

Statistical Analysis to Support Improved Student Outcomes

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Abstract

A supply of individuals trained in STEM is needed to meet the employment needs of the United States. To address this need, an analytics initiative was executed to analyze multiple data streams relevant to education and learning. The goal of this effort was to identify factors that impact educational outcomes. Knowledge about these factors can potentially be used to improve the educational environment. This investigation makes use of big data and analytics to build predictive models for improving student success. Data is used to help understand how children, adolescents, and adults progress throughout the education system. Though additional study and verification of the factors identified by the models is recommended, knowledge of factors affecting students with different attributes could be a powerful source of information for addressing the needs of students and helping them to achieve successful outcomes such as on-time high school graduation, higher education degree completion, and STEM degree completion. Putting knowledge about different effects into action can pave the way for increasing the number of individuals who complete high school, college, and STEM degrees.

Key Words: education, data analytics, statistical modeling, quality improvement

1. Introduction

The University of Texas System (UTS) conceived of and initiated the Education and Learning Analytics Project as part of its strategic goals, called Quantum Leaps. Part of Quantum Leaps is the Texas Prospect Initiative. The goals of this initiative are to: Deepen UTS engagement in improving student outcomes PK-20; engender bold change and systemic reform through unprecedented collaboration and partnerships; and align the UTS's work with the Texas Higher Education Coordinating Board's 60X30TX Campaign, with its economic and moral imperative to educate more Texas children with 21st-century skills and knowledge.

One of the first projects emerging from the Texas Prospect Initiative is called the Education and Learning Analytics Project funded by UTS. This project is led by Dr. Pedro Reyes as the Primary Investigator, the University of Texas Education Research Center (ERC) staff, and Steven Stringer and Joanne Wendelberger from Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL). The purpose of this project is to use big data and analytics to build predictive models to improve student success in PK-20+ systems. This project requires many years-worth of student-level data similar to the information contained in the P-20/Workforce Data Repository. This data is used to help understand how children, adolescents, and adults progress throughout the education system. The data is also used to conduct advanced analytics to reliably predict educational outcomes at scale for all sectors of the education pipeline. Better understanding of individual and system-wide progress can inform decision-making to provide opportunities for individuals to reach their full potential [See Chetty et al, 2014] while contributing to economic prosperity and stability.

A Cooperative Research and Development Agreement was established between University of Texas at Austin (UT Austin) and Los Alamos National Laboratory to investigate Education and Learning Analytics. This collaboration combines the educational expertise and data resources of the Education Research Center at University of Texas at Austin with the analytical and computational expertise of Los Alamos National Laboratory. The agreement specifies a plan involving an initial feasibility study to lay groundwork for potential follow-on studies. The results of the initial feasibility study are presented here.

2. Approach

The Scope of Work defined in the CRADA for the feasibility study specified a set of five tasks to enable execution of an analysis and modeling effort to provide insights and understanding into the factors that affect high school outcomes, postsecondary degree completion, and STEM degree completion. The set of tasks addressed Data Source Identification and Aggregation, Data Access and Privacy Assurance, Data Analysis and Characterization, Data Synthesis and Reporting, and Data Disposition.

2.1 Data Source Identification and Aggregation

The ERC compiles and maintains extensive data resources with information relevant to educational experiences and outcomes from Pre-Kindergarten through high school, higher education, and beyond. Guided by ERC staff, key data sets and variables were selected, and features were constructed for modeling. Data extracted from various sources were assembled to provide a variety of explanatory input variables and a number of outcome variables associated with educational progress and degree completion. The Appendix provides a summary of the variables used in this study.

2.2 Data Access and Privacy Assurance

Data access and privacy assurance requires appropriate handling of data to ensure that Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act (FERPA) Requirements and U.S. Department of Energy Human Subjects Requirements are met. LANL has worked with UT Austin to ensure that appropriate documentation was prepared and updated to maintain approval for project activities. The LANL Human Subjects Research Review Board periodically reviewed the project and provided Institutional Review Board (IRB) Review/Waiver status.

Computer access was established to allow LANL researchers to remotely log in to ERC computers to access data within an approved protected environment. The ERC provides a secure environment for access to the data and a well-defined procedure for review and release of information to protect information about individuals and ensure FERPA compliance.

2.3 Data Analysis and Characterization

Exploratory analysis was conducted to understand the populations in the K12 cohorts of interest and the different variables that are available for modeling and analysis. Extensive statistical modeling was conducted to model high school outcomes as a function of information about individual students. Analysis was also conducted to examine the relationship between higher education outcomes and individual student level information.

2.4 Data Synthesis and Reporting

A graphical model was developed to characterize the flow of students through K12 and Higher Education. The graphical model provides a visual representation of the paths by which students complete bachelor's degrees and STEM degrees and the probabilities of advancing along the different paths. Results of the analyses that were conducted are described later in this report.

2.5 Data Disposition

All raw data resides on the ERC server. Analysis of the raw data is conducted on the ERC's computer systems. Results of analyses are submitted for FERPA review before being made available outside of the ERC computing environment. These results may then be incorporated into further analysis and documentation. Information is released outside of ERC and LANL only upon review and approval by ERC and LANL. At the conclusion of the LANL/UT ERC CRADA project, there is no further access to the original raw data by the LANL team members.

3. Description of Data

In 2006, the Texas Legislature authorized the creation of Education Research Centers (ERCs) to house Texas data and facilitate research that benefits all levels of education in Texas. The ERCs provide access to high quality, student-level data from the Texas Education Agency (TEA), the Texas Higher Education Coordinating Board (THECB), the Texas Workforce Commission, and other sources of information for the state. The data sources are combined using a unique identifier for each student. Data used for this study is maintained by the University of Texas at Austin Education Research Center.

The data available for this study includes extensive information for three different cohorts of students entering kindergarten for the first time in Texas public schools in the years 1995, 1998, and 2000. The 1995 cohort includes 252,115 students. The 1998 cohort includes 268,668 students. The 2000 cohort includes 265,368 students.

Cohorts were chosen by examining state policy changes over time regarding graduation requirements for the state. These graduation plans are legislated in Texas and are referred to as required "core" courses. Cohort 1995 corresponds to the Pre 4x4 graduation plan, Cohort 1998 the Modified 4x4 plan, and Cohort 2000 the 4x4 plan.

The **Pre 4x4 Recommended & Distinguished** plan requires four English courses (English 1-4), three mathematics courses (Algebra 1, Algebra 2, Geometry), three science courses (one each of Biology, Chemistry, and Physics courses), and four Social Studies/Economics courses. The minimum plan requires four English courses (with choice of elective on the fourth course), three Mathematics courses with Algebra 2 being optional, two Science courses, and three Social Studies/Economics courses. All 3 plans have .5 more PE, .5 of speech, a 1.0 technology course and fewer electives compared to the two plans described below.

The **Modified Pre 4x4** plan handles English, Mathematics, Science, and Social Studies/Economics in the same manner as the Pre 4x4 plan, but there are fewer additional requirements as noted above.

The **4x4 Recommended & Distinguished** plans require four courses each of English, Mathematics (including Algebra2), Science, and Social Studies/Economics. The Minimum plan requires four English courses, three Mathematics courses (Algebra2 optional with course choices for replacement), two Science Courses, and three Social Studies/Economics courses.

4. Methodology

4.1 Dataset Creation

Multiple steps were taken to create the datasets for each of the three cohorts used for the analysis. First, decisions were made regarding what types of indicators or factors across the education pipeline were thought to influence whether a student ultimately obtains a Bachelor's degree in a STEM field. Second, students in these three cohorts of kindergartners were followed for the subsequent twelve years of public school and then six years of college. Data for Pre-Kindergarten (Pre-K) was also included. Students were followed for as many years as data existed, up to twenty years if they were enrolled Pre-K through 12th grade and were enrolled in higher education for the following six years.

The factors considered relevant for Pre-K through 12th grade years utilized student data from files provided by the TEA that covered demographics, enrollment, standardized test performance, STEM coursework, and graduation/exit. These variables were collected and merged together for each cohort across each of the fourteen years that were pertinent to the type of factor. For example, all years of enrollment were included, but only the high school years were included to determine on-time graduation.

Higher education data were also merged into the cohort datasets and were collected across the six years following on-time high school graduation. Data from Texas higher education institutions were included from THECB, and data for graduates who attended college out of state were included from the National Student Clearinghouse. Relevant factors for predicting STEM degree attainment utilized files covering higher education enrollment, graduation, and type of major.

4.2 Data Visualization and Exploratory Analysis

Visualizations were developed, and exploratory analyses were conducted to develop familiarity with the data and to examine different analysis approaches.

Figures 1-3 display the makeup of the three cohorts over time. These figures provide visual representations of student enrollment from each of the cohorts progressing from kindergarten (or in some cases Pre-K) through 12th grade over time. As students in each cohort progress through school, the number of students in the cohort in a particular grade will change over time based on the progress of the students and the changing population over time. As shown in Figure 1, most students advance one grade each year. However, others will drop out or exit the system for various reasons, while others may be retained and end up in a different grade than their original peer group.

The largest portion of each vertical bar captures the flow of students who remain in the system and advance one grade each year. Smaller portions of the vertical bars correspond to students who were retained one or more years. Since a cohort only includes students who started kindergarten in the specified year, the total number of students remaining in the on-time group gradually decreases, as students are either retained or exit. The spike at ninth grade is associated with the relatively large number of students who do not move on to tenth grade on schedule as more stringent requirements are imposed when the students reach high school. Comparison of Figures 1 to 3 indicates that the pattern of student counts over time is strikingly similar across the three cohorts. This pattern provides some insights into the paths that students take and illustrates how the student population in a cohort evolves over time, thus impacting the overall rate of on-time graduation for the cohort. This behavior helped to motivate the need for closer examination of student progression and high school outcomes with a focus on the rate of on-time graduation.

Cohort 1995

Figure 1: Progression is shown for students from the 1995 cohort over time. Students enter cohort in kindergarten (or in some cases in Pre-K programs) and move through the system.

Cohort 1998

Figure 2: Progression is shown for students from the 1998 cohort over time. Students enter cohort in kindergarten (or in some cases in Pre-K programs) and move through the system.

Figure 3: Progression is shown for students from the 2000 cohort over time. Students enter cohort in kindergarten (or in some cases in Pre-K programs) and move through the system.

Exploratory analyses were also conducted to examine what approaches might be useful for gaining insight into factors that might explain outcomes in education, such as whether or not a student graduated from high school. These preliminary analyses were used to examine a small set of variables expected to potentially impact the outcome of interest: whether or not students achieved on-time high school graduation. This initial modeling focused on a small set of variables including income status, special education participation, gifted education participation, and English Language Learner Status. In these early studies, whether a student came from a low-income family was examined at different years across PK-12, and whether or not a student was designated low income in one or more years across PK-12 was identified as a significant factor to be considered for more in-depth modeling.

Two different approaches, parametric modeling and tree-based modeling, were implemented for predicting whether students graduate high school on time. Logistic regression is a parametric modeling approach that specifies a statistical model with parameters that are estimated from the data. The resulting model can be used to predict a binary outcome of on-time high school graduation versus not graduating on time as a function of various education variables [Agresti, 2019]. Tree-based models offer a nonparametric alternative [Breiman et al, 2001]. Recursive partitioning of the variable space is conducted by performing a series of binary splits of model variables with the goal of correctly classifying observations as one of the possible binary outcomes associated with a student either graduating on time or not. An extension of traditional single tree solutions is the ensemble random forest approach which generates many trees from different populations that are generated in a random manner from the original single sample [Breiman, 2001; Hastie et al, 2008].

These initial models provided an opportunity to become familiar with the available data and suggested that logistic modeling might be useful, as well as its multivariate extension, multinomial logistic regression, which can jointly model categorical variables with multiple outcomes by modeling logs of ratios of probabilities of being in different categories as a linear combination of the input variables.

Figure 4 shows a Recursive Partitioning Tree that was generated for Cohort 1998, with an initial split based on whether students were low income in primary grades and subsequent splits based on variables such as special education status, English Language Learner status and At Risk of dropping out status at different points in student careers. While the graphical representations are interesting, their structure can be inconsistent across different populations and samples. With large numbers of variables, the trees can become very complex and difficult to interpret.

It is not surprising that income appeared to be important in both the tree-based and parametric approaches. However, since income cannot easily be changed, there was a desire to pursue methods that would support inclusion of a variety of inputs without necessarily ending up with fits dominated by an initial split on income. Experimentation with these approaches and examination of scientific literature [Mare, 1981; Jones-White et al, 2010; Karlson et al, 2011] led to the selection of a multinomial logistic regression approach for predicting educational outcomes as a function of predictor variables within a broader framework that could connect the results from different parts of the educational pipeline.

Figure 4: Recursive partitioning was used to generate tree-based models based on binary splits aimed at predicting whether or not On-Time High School Graduation was achieved.

4.3 Modeling Plan

An important step in the STEM production modeling process was to develop a conceptual model of the educational process for producing STEM trained individuals. Figure 5 provides a schematic of the educational pipeline that captures the evolution of student educational careers over time as different factors come into play. Students enter the system in the early education phase of Pre-K or Kindergarten and then move forward through primary grades, middle school, high school, and higher education. Ultimately, they reach a high school outcome, and subsequently may go on to higher education, possibly earning a STEM degree.

Key Milestones on the Education Pipeline that (Likely) Predict Achieving a STEM Degree

Figure 5: Conceptual model of the educational pipeline for STEM Degree/Certificate Completion

For modeling purposes, a simplified schematic shown in Figure 6 was developed to capture key phases in this overall pipeline. Rather than attempting to model completion of a STEM degree directly from end-to-end, when many of the students do not travel through the complete path, the decision was made to examine the steps leading to a STEM degree and seek variables that would help predict the likelihood of successful completion of different phases.

Figure 6: Graphical representation of a three-stage education pipeline for Bachelor's STEM Degrees

The first key step along the modeling pathway was to model high school graduation outcomes. Focus could then be placed on high school graduates who went on to enroll in higher education programs, complete higher education programs, and potentially earn STEM degrees.

The initial outcome studied was the high school outcome represented by a variable named HSOutcome, a categorical variable with the following five categories: Graduate, Dropout, Other Leaver, Still in School, and Unknown Status.

HSOutcome counts for Cohort 2000 were as follows:

Graduate	Dropout	Other Leaver	Still in School	Unknown
159,964	13,201	25,088	37,719	29,396

Counts of students at different stages of the educational pipeline can be used to calculate estimates of the probabilities of students following specific directed segments within the graph by taking the fraction of students taking an individual path at a decision point divided by the total number of students who arrive at that decision point. The resulting estimates can then be used to quantify the rate of flow of students along the different paths, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Graphical representation of the educational pipeline for Bachelor’s STEM Degrees with estimated probabilities of different segments at selected decision nodes

Probability estimates along a path with multiple segments can then be used to calculate the probability that a student will take a specific path by multiplying together the probability of selecting the initial segment on the path with the conditional probabilities of staying on the specified path at each decision point.

The overall probability of a student obtaining a Bachelor’s STEM Degree is calculated as follows:

Using the notation $P(B|A)$ for the conditional probability that event B occurs given that A has occurred,

$P(\text{Bachelor's STEM Degree})$

$$= P(A) * P(B|A) * P(C|B)$$

$$= P(\text{HSOutcome}=\text{Grad}) * P(\text{Bachelor's Degree}|\text{HSOutcome}=\text{Grad}) * P(\text{STEM Degree}|\text{Bachelor's Degree}),$$

where A indicates the event (HSOutcome=Grad),
 B indicates the event (Bachelor's Degree is obtained),
 and C indicates the event (STEM Degree is obtained).

For Cohort 2000, $P(\text{Bachelor's STEM Degree}) = .60 * .26 * .22 = .03432 = 3.432\%$.
 If there were 100,000 kindergartners, we would expect 3,432 to follow this path.

This means that estimates of the probability of a STEM degree can be obtained using either the counts associated with the initial states and the final states of the overall path or by using the estimates obtained from the counts of the individual students taking different paths at the decision points along the path. Because only a small fraction of the students will follow any individual complete path, using the conditional probabilities of the segments allows incorporation of data from all students who go through one or more of the decision points along the path, rather than just the data for the students who remain in the system all the way through the final decision point.

Figure 8: Graphical representation of the educational pipeline for Bachelor's STEM Degrees with estimated probabilities of segments at selected decision nodes and a series of directed red segments highlighting a STEM Degree Completion Path from Kindergarten to High School Graduation to Bachelor's Degree and STEM Degree Completion

The graphical framework provides a path forward for using data not only to quantify the numbers of students flowing through the system, but also as a mechanism for understanding and potentially influencing the rate of STEM Degree production. The

paths in the figure show key points in the process that can be further modeled using student data to identify factors that influence the probabilities that students will take paths that lead to STEM degrees. At each key point, a student can end up in different categories. Multinomial logistic regression is a statistical method that can be used for modeling the probabilities of discrete outcomes as a function of explanatory variables. This method was selected to examine the impact of various educational factors and metrics on the outcomes of students based on the structure of the STEM production pipeline, our preliminary analysis work, and examination of the statistical and educational literature on previous education modeling efforts.

4.4 Multinomial Logistic Regression

Multinomial logistic regression uses the same logic as binary logistic regression, in that it is used to model a discrete categorical outcome variable in which the log odds of the outcomes are modeled as a linear combination of the education predictor variables. Unlike binary logistic regression, however, where only two categories can be modeled (such as graduated yes/no), the outcome variable of interest for multiple logistic regression may have three or more categories. One of the categories is designated a reference category, and all other categories are individually modeled in comparison to the reference category. In the following analyses that are intended to develop predictive models for on-time high school graduation, categories such as ‘dropout’ and ‘still in school’ are compared to the reference category of high school graduation. Using this convention, the analysis shows how high school graduates differ from each of the other groups’ categories on the education variables of interest. Examining this set of results leads to the most nuanced understanding of on-time high school graduation. This level of understanding is required to develop and implement recommendations for substantive improvements in the rates of successful student outcomes at multiple points along their educational paths.

4.5 Modeling High School Outcomes for 2000 Kindergarten Cohort

Following the exploratory analysis, a more comprehensive modeling study was conducted to develop models for high school outcomes as a function of predictor variables for the 2000 Cohort. Starting from a relatively small set of predictors, a multinomial logistic regression model was used to predict high school outcome categories as a function of increasing amounts of information about students.

Five initial input data sets were used that incorporated increasing sets of predictor variables through the selection of input variables anticipated to predict students’ high school outcomes. As the modeling process continued, a sixth data set was added, which judiciously removed some variables, to improve the usefulness of the model as described below. Table 1 displays the different variables in the series of six models used to iteratively search for models with predictive capability and interpretability.

Table 1: Input Variables for the Multinomial Logistic Regression Models Used in the Investigation of High School Outcomes

Input Variables in Model	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
Male	X	X	X	X	X	X
Black	X	X	X	X	X	X
Hispanic	X	X	X	X	X	X
Native American	X	X	X	X	X	X
Asian	X	X	X	X	X	X
Spanish Language	X	X	X	X	X	X
Other Language	X	X	X	X	X	X
English Learner	X	X	X	X	X	X
Dropout Risk	X	X	X	X	X	X
Special Education	X	X	X	X	X	X
Gifted	X	X	X	X	X	X
Low Income	X	X	X	X	X	X
Pre-K		X	X	X	X	X
Pre-K Non-eligible		X	X	X	X	X
Grade Retention			X	X	X	
Enrollment			X	X	X	
Primary Grade Enrollment			X	X	X	X
Mobility			X	X	X	X
Reading Test Grade 3					X	X
Reading Score Grade 3				X	X'	X'
Math Test Grade 5					X	X
Math Score Grade 5				X	X'	X'
Reading Test Grade 6					X	X
Reading Score Grade 6				X	X'	X'
Math Test Grade 8					X	X
Math Score Grade 8				X	X'	X'

Note: High School Outcome models created with the same number in their names have the same set of input variables. X' = Scaled Score if available, 0 Otherwise.

The final model that was selected makes use of the Model 6 input variables. The process by which the model inputs, model outputs, relevant population, and estimation methods were selected will be described in further detail in the Modeling section, including a discussion of modeling issues that were encountered and technical approaches for addressing them.

5. Modeling

5.1 Initial Modeling

Initial modeling of high school outcomes for the 2000 K12 Student Cohort made use of the first five sets of model inputs in Table 1 to model High School Outcome via a multinomial logistic regression approach implemented in the R statistical software *nnet* package [Ripley, 2020]. As expected, our iterative modeling approach which incorporated additional variables was able to improve predictive capability, but technical issues were also encountered that needed to be addressed such as missing values, disparate predictive capability arising from unequal counts in different categories, selection of an appropriate population to include in the modeling, suspected correlations between different variables, and difficulty in discriminating between categories that may exhibit similar behavior. Below, we describe some of the modeling behavior that was encountered during our iterative modeling process and our rationale on how to proceed with the modeling process.

5.2 Weighted Models

The models constructed to predict the high school outcome (Outcome variable HSOOutcome) tended to classify a disproportionately large number of observations in the categories with the most students. One way to adjust for this issue is to perform a weighted analysis, as denoted in the Estimation Method column in Table 2 below. Weights were scaled according to the inverse of the counts of individuals in the sample population for each category.

5.3 Removal of Records with Unknown Outcomes

The initial models made use of data from all students in the population. Due to the occurrence of student mobility and a variety of other reasons, many students do not have complete information for all of the variables. In particular, a large number of students have an Unknown high school outcome, typically because these students permanently left the Texas public school system during their primary school years. Thus, models were rerun using a new outcome variable, HSOOutcomeNoU, created by removing the individuals with Unknown outcomes as denoted by the Population utilized.

5.4 Incorporating Test Scores

The progression of models incorporates student test scores at the Model 4 stage. Simply adding the scaled scores to the model was problematic, because there were many students who did not have scores available. In order to capitalize on the potential predictive capability of test scores, while retaining as many records as possible, an indicator variable was created for each test that was coded as 1 if a particular student had no test score and 0 otherwise. A second variable was created from the original scaled score variable for each test that was the same as the original score if available and 0 otherwise. This pair of variables uses a simple fill-in approach that allows the model to use the actual scores when available while estimating an overall average effect for the students who lack test scores. Together, the use of the indicator variable and fill-in variable preserve the ability to retain information about test scores and other variables from individual students in the analysis, despite lack of information about test scores for some individuals.

5.5 Combined Dropouts and Other Leavers

By combining a number of different modeling approaches, later models were obtained that had much better predictive capability than the initial models. However, it was noted that the models consistently had difficulty in discriminating between Dropouts and Other Leavers. Thus, Dropouts and Leavers were combined into a single category (Outcome variable HSOOutcomeX), and all model variants were run. An additional outcome variable, HSOOutcomeXNoU, was created that combined dropouts and other leavers and also applied the removal of students with unknown outcomes as described previously for HSOOutcomeNoU.

5.6 Selective Removal of Input Variables

Upon examination of the initial set of forty runs obtained using the four different outcome variables, the five different model input sets, and the weighted and unweighted estimation techniques, it was noted that two of the input variables, Enrollment and Grade Retention dominated, obscuring the effects of other variables of interest. Logically, these variables would be expected to be highly redundant with the high school outcome that was being modeled. A student who is retained in a grade is most often not able to graduate on time. Similarly, to graduate on time, a student in the cohort would generally need to be enrolled for the full thirteen years. Including these variables leads to models that are highly predictive but not necessarily useful. A sixth input data set was created by removing these two variables from the model, and all model variants arising from the four different outcome variables, two population selection options, and two estimation schemes were run, resulting in a total of 48 models. Table 1 provides details on the model specification, choice of estimation method, sample population, number of records used, fit statistics Residual Deviance and AIC, and overall prediction rate. Table 2 provides a summary of the K12 models for Cohort 2000 that were implemented in the study. Note that within each sequential set of six runs, the Residual Deviance and AIC values tend to decrease from Model 1 to Model 2 to Model 3, go up with Model 4 as information from observations with missing test scores are lost, and then continue to decrease with Model 5. Finally, the removal of the Retention and K12 Enrollment Variables in Model 6 improves interpretability but leads to increased fitting error and decreased predictive power. In general, the predictions from these smaller models still perform reasonably well across the different categories despite some reduction in overall predictive power.

Table 3 provides more detailed information about the predictive rates for the K12 model runs. The rate of correct prediction is shown for each category of a specified model along with the overall rate of correct prediction across all categories (see Table 3).

Table 4 provides a cross-tabulation of the actual and predicted numbers of students in the different categories, along with the rates of correct classification within categories and overall for K12model6XNoUw. Overall classification for K12model6XNoUw is very close to that for K12model5NoU, but K12model6XNoU performs better across the different categories. The rate of correct classification for Dropouts has increased from 0.106 to 0.519, while the other rates drop slightly, giving a better picture overall. K12model6XNoUw was selected as the final model.

Table 2: Summary of K12 Models for Cohort 2000

Model	Input Set	Outcome Variable	Wts/ No Wts	Popu- Lation	Records Used	Residual Deviance	AIC	Pred. Rate
1	1	HSOut	U	All	265,368	574,235	574,339	.603
2	2	HSOut	U	All	265,368	570,867	570,987	.607
3	3	HSOut	U	All	265,368	272,728	272,880	.830
4	4	HSOut	U	All	157,650	97,512	97,696	.900
5	5	HSOut	U	All	265,368	252,017	252,233	.844
6	6	HSOut	U	All	265,368	371,613	371,813	.786
1w	1	HSOut	W	All	265,368	3,795,468	3,795,572	.328
2w	2	HSOut	W	All	265,368	3,780,635	3,780,755	.336
3w	3	HSOut	W	All	265,368	2,203,424	2,203,576	.822
4w	4	HSOut	W	All	157,650	750,974	751,158	.860
5w	5	HSOut	W	All	265,368	2,117,958	2,118,174	.817
6w	6	HSOut	W	All	265,368	2,909,872	2,910,072	.703
1NoU	1	HSOutNoU	U	No Unk	235,972	410,119	410,197	.678
2NoU	2	HSOutNoU	U	No Unk	235,972	408,860	408,950	.679
3NoU	3	HSOutNoU	U	No Unk	235,972	225,369	225,483	.837
4NoU	4	HSOutNoU	U	No Unk	156,015	85,698	85,836	.909
5NoU	5	HSOutNoU	U	No Unk	235,972	205,240	205,402	.850
6NoU	6	HSOutNoU	U	No Unk	235,972	296,622	296,772	.795
1NoUw	1	HSOutNoU	W	No Unk	235,972	2,413,225	2,413,303	.412
2NoUw	2	HSOutNoU	W	No Unk	235,972	2,407,326	2,407,416	.455
3NoUw	3	HSOutNoU	W	No Unk	235,972	1,558,199	1,558,313	.828
4NoUw	4	HSOutNoU	W	No Unk	156,015	572,081	572,219	.869
5NoUw	5	HSOutNoU	W	No Unk	235,972	1,489,506	1,489,668	.820
6NoUw	6	HSOutNoU	W	No Unk	235,972	2,037,618	2,037,768	.701
1X	1	HSOutX	U	All	265,368	529,085	529,163	.603
2X	2	HSOutX	U	All	265,368	525,751	525,841	.607
3X	3	HSOutX	U	All	265,368	229,302	229,416	.860
4X	4	HSOutX	U	All	157,650	81,776	81,914	.915
5X	5	HSOutX	U	All	265,368	209,121	209,283	.874
6X	6	HSOutX	U	All	265,368	327,288	327,438	.789
1Xw	1	HSOutX	W	All	265,368	2,587,420	2,587,498	.372
2Xw	2	HSOutX	W	All	265,368	2,574,337	2,574,427	.379
3Xw	3	HSOutX	W	All	265,368	1,187,087	1,187,201	.855
4Xw	4	HSOutX	W	All	157,650	399,586	399,724	.888
5Xw	5	HSOutX	W	All	265,368	1,120,091	1,120,253	.854
6Xw	6	HSOutX	W	All	265,368	1,752,387	1,752,537	.750
1XNoU	1	HSOutXNoU	U	No Unk	235,972	364,910	364,962	.678
2XNoU	2	HSOutXNoU	U	No Unk	235,972	363,670	363,730	.679
3XNoU	3	HSOutXNoU	U	No Unk	235,972	182,211	182,287	.872
4XNoU	4	HSOutXNoU	U	No Unk	156,015	69,903	69,995	.924
5XNoU	5	HSOutXNoU	U	No Unk	235,972	162,549	162,657	.885
6NoU	6	HSOutXNoU	U	No Unk	235,972	252,270	252,370	.799
1XNoUw	1	HSOutXNoU	W	No Unk	235,972	1,422,350	1,422,402	.478
2XNoUw	2	HSOutXNoU	W	No Unk	235,972	1,418,497	1,418,557	.512
3XNoUw	3	HSOutXNoU	W	No Unk	235,972	733,824	733,900	.869
4XNoUw	4	HSOutXNoU	W	No Unk	156,015	273,767	273,859	.898
5XNoUw	5	HSOutXNoU	W	No Unk	235,972	679,071	679,179	.866
6XNoUw	6	HSOutXNoU	W	No Unk	235,972	1,080,203	1,080,303	.758

Table 3: Prediction Rates for K12 Models for Cohort 2000

Rate of Correct Predictions	Rate of Correct Predictions						
	Graduates	Dropouts	Leavers	Dropouts/Leavers	Still In School	Unknown	Overall
1	0.974	0.000	0.000		0.109	0.003	0.603
2	0.975	0.000	0.000		0.084	0.060	0.607
3	0.918	0.119	0.488		0.895	0.878	0.830
4	0.989	0.148	0.598		0.093	0.000	0.900
5	0.965	0.102	0.466		0.813	0.876	0.844
6	0.964	0.003	0.066		0.779	0.793	0.786
1w	0.293	0.491	0.203		0.366	0.505	0.328
2w	0.303	0.483	0.205		0.371	0.513	0.336
3w	0.893	0.423	0.428		0.881	0.876	0.822
4w	0.922	0.505	0.605		0.312	0.000	0.860
5w	0.893	0.512	0.445		0.806	0.874	0.817
6w	0.800	0.321	0.162		0.708	0.799	0.703
1NoU	0.974	0.000	0.000		0.109		0.678
2NoU	0.984	0.000	0.000		0.077		0.679
3NoU	0.919	0.140	0.592		0.896		0.837
4NoU	0.989	0.150	0.595		0.093		0.909
5NoU	0.966	0.106	0.562		0.813		0.850
6NoU	0.965	0.003	0.127		0.793		0.795
1NoUw	0.444	0.491	0.236		0.365		0.412
2NoUw	0.520	0.483	0.226		0.322		0.455
3NoUw	0.895	0.427	0.535		0.879		0.828
4NoUw	0.922	0.522	0.600		0.279		0.869
5NoUw	0.893	0.519	0.537		0.805		0.820
6NoUw	0.802	0.331	0.234		0.715		0.701
1X	0.974			0.000	0.109	0.003	0.603
2X	0.976			0.000	0.083	0.060	0.607
3X	0.917			0.578	0.890	0.874	0.860
4X	0.989			0.614	0.086	0.000	0.915
5X	0.961			0.587	0.797	0.872	0.874
6X	0.962			0.100	0.750	0.787	0.789
1Xw	0.298			0.275	0.679	0.505	0.372
2Xw	0.311			0.309	0.635	0.513	0.379
3Xw	0.898			0.620	0.890	0.879	0.855
4Xw	0.924			0.736	0.634	0.000	0.888
5Xw	0.897			0.653	0.856	0.879	0.854
6Xw	0.858			0.247	0.755	0.806	0.750
1XNoU	0.974			0.000	0.109		0.678
2XNoU	0.984			0.000	0.077		0.679
3XNoU	0.918			0.661	0.890		0.872
4XNoU	0.989			0.612	0.087		0.924
5XNoU	0.962			0.652	0.797		0.885
6XNoU	0.964			0.154	0.758		0.799
1XNoUw	0.478			0.346	0.612		0.478
2XNoUw	0.542			0.348	0.552		0.512
3XNoUw	0.900			0.717	0.891		0.869
4XNoUw	0.926			0.731	0.633		0.898
5XNoUw	0.899			0.740	0.857		0.866
6XNoUw	0.861			0.321	0.765		0.758

Table 4: Classification Performance for Final Multinomial Logistic Model with Graduates Used as Reference Group, Observations with Unknown High School Outcomes Omitted, and Estimation Performed Using Weighted Method.

K12Model6XNoUw	Predicted Graduate	Predicted Dropout/Other Leaver	Predicted Still in School	Rate of Correct Classification
Actual Graduate	137,714	18,182	4,068	.861
Actual Dropout/OtherLeaver	12,253	12,298	13,738	.321
Actual Still In School	3,701	5,166	28,852	.765

Overall Correct Classification Rate = .758

The discussion thus far has focused primarily on the Classification Rates of the individual models in terms of correct classification overall and correct classification within the different categories that are relevant for each model. Additional model diagnostics associated with the effects of the different input variables were calculated to provide further information about each model. These statistics included coefficients, standard errors, Z-scores, Odds Ratios, and Inverse Log Odds Ratios. Tables 5 and 6 provide information about variable effects for the final model, K12Model6XNoUw. Figures 9 and 10 provide bar graphs of the coefficients, Z-scores, odds ratios, and inverse odds ratios.

In Table 5, the coefficients arise from the model of the log of the ratio of the probability of being in the comparison Dropout/Leaver category to the probability of the reference On-time Graduate category as a linear function of the predictor variables. Similarly, Table 6 provides analogous information for the Still In School comparison category versus the reference On-time Graduation category. Taking the ratio of a coefficient to its Standard Error provides a Z-Score statistic and associated p-value. Larger Z-scores (say, larger than around 2) and smaller p values (probability of an effect of this size being observed when there is no effect) suggest statistically significant effects. Due to the large numbers of observations and large numbers of predictors being used in these models, it is not surprising to see nearly all effects showing up as highly significant.

The coefficients, odds ratios (labeled as OR), and inverse odds ratios (labeled as 1/OR) can be used to identify influential factors. For a given factor, the odds ratio indicates how likely the comparison group is relative to the reference group. Factors with a positive coefficient will have an odds ratio greater than one, indicating a higher probability of being in the comparison group than the reference group [UCLA, 2021]. Similarly, factors with a negative coefficient will have an odds ratio less than one, indicating a lower probability of being in the comparison group than the reference group. A factor with an odds ratio of two indicates that it is 100% more likely or twice as likely that an individual with that factor will be in the comparison group than the reference group.

As an example, in Table 5, the odds ratio for Male is 1.272. This means that males have 27.2% higher odds of being a Leaver (versus a Graduate) than females. When odds ratios are less than one, then the inverse of the odds ratio can be used to see how much more likely it is that an individual is in the reference group rather than the comparison group. A student who is Asian, as opposed to being White, will have 41% higher odds of graduating than leaving as compared to white students.

To find factors that may be most influential in impacting dropouts and other leavers relative to the graduates, one can look for factors associated with the highest odds of graduating (odds ratio small and <1) and the lowest odds of graduating (odds ratio large and > 1).

For Dropouts/Other Leavers compared to Graduates:

Students who were *Male*, *Native American*, with a high *Dropout Risk*, who were *Low Income*, had a high degree of *Mobility*, and had lower scores on the *ReadingTestGrade 3*, have the largest odds ratios and the lowest odds of graduating.

Conversely, *Black*, *Hispanic*, *Asian* students who speak an *OtherLanguage* at home, have a *PreK* experience, and have higher test scores on the *MathTestGrade5*, *Reading TestGrade6*, *MathTestGrade8* tests, have the smallest odds ratios and the highest odds of graduating.

For Still In School compared to Graduates:

Students who were *Male*, had a high *Dropout Risk*, were *Gifted*, had continuous *Primary Grade Enrollment*, but had higher *Mobility*, have the largest odds ratios and the lowest odds of graduating.

Conversely, students who were *Black*, in *SpecialEducation*, and who had higher scores on the *ReadingTestGrade3*, *MathTestGrade5*, *ReadingTestGrade6*, *MathTestGrade8* tests, have the smallest odds ratios and the highest odds of graduating.

Comparing these lists, *the variables Male, Dropout Risk, and Mobility* are associated with lower odds of graduating for both Dropout/Other Leaver and Still in School. *Black, MathTestGrade5, Reading TestGrade6, MathTestGrade8* are associated with higher odds of graduating for both Dropout/Other Leaver and Still in School *categories*.

Table 5: Final Multinomial Logistic Regression Model K12model6XNoUw:
Dropout/OtherLeavers vs Graduates

DROPOUT/ OTHERLEAVER	Coef	StdError	Z	p	OR	1/OR
Male	0.2409	0.003571	67.47	0.0000	1.272	0.786
Black	-0.5321	0.003065	-173.58	0.0000	0.587	1.703
Hispanic	-0.3042	0.003508	-86.70	0.0000	0.738	1.355
NativeAmerican	0.2259	0.000567	398.44	0.0000	1.253	0.798
Asian	-0.3390	0.000583	-581.18	0.0000	0.712	1.404
Spanish	0.0181	0.002941	6.17	0.0000	1.018	0.982
OtherLanguage	-0.4102	0.000571	-718.09	0.0000	0.664	1.507
EnglishLearner	-0.1316	0.003052	-43.14	0.0000	0.877	1.141
DropoutRisk	0.2346	0.001496	156.81	0.0000	1.264	0.791
SpecialEducation	-0.1696	0.003962	-42.80	0.0000	0.844	1.185
Gifted	0.0234	0.000950	24.61	0.0000	1.024	0.977
LowIncome	0.3749	0.002778	134.94	0.0000	1.455	0.687
PreK	-0.3974	0.003413	-116.43	0.0000	0.672	1.488
PreKNonEligible	-0.1742	0.004130	-42.19	0.0000	0.840	1.190
PrimaryGradeEnrollment	-0.0056	0.002551	-2.18	0.0289	0.994	1.006
Mobility	0.3070	0.003199	95.98	0.0000	1.359	0.736
ReadingTestGrade3	0.3318	0.000640	518.70	0.0000	1.393	0.718
ReadingScoreGrade3	0.0001	0.000006	19.78	0.0000	1.000	1.000
MathTestGrade5	-0.2165	0.000608	-356.27	0.0000	0.805	1.242
MathScoreGrade5	-0.0002	0.000007	-25.13	0.0000	1.000	1.000
ReadingTestGrade6	-1.0882	0.000635	-1,714.72	0.0000	0.337	2.969
ReadingScoreGrade6	-0.0005	0.000007	-68.58	0.0000	1.000	1.000
MathTestGrade8	-3.2374	0.000596	-5,432.27	0.0000	0.039	25.467
MathScoreGrade8	-0.0029	0.000006	-445.58	0.0000	0.997	1.003

Large Odds Ratios (lower chance of graduating) include: *Male, Native American, Dropout Risk, Low Income, Mobility, ReadingTestGrade3.*

Large Inverse Odds Ratios (higher chance of graduating) include: *Black, Hispanic, Asian, OtherLanguage, PreK, MathTestGrade5, ReadingTestGrade6, MathTestGrade8.*

Figure 9: Bar graphs of coefficients, Z-Scores, odds ratios, and inverse odds ratios for final model, K12model6XNoUw, Dropouts/Other Leavers vs. Graduates

Table 6: Results for Final Multinomial Logistic Regression Model K12model6XNoUw:
Still in School vs Graduates

STILL IN SCHOOL	Coef	StdError	Z	p	OR	1/OR
Male	0.4293	0.002766	155.19	0.0000	1.536	0.651
Black	-0.1412	0.002490	-56.72	0.0000	0.868	1.152
Hispanic	-0.0452	0.003393	-13.31	0.0000	0.956	1.046
NativeAmerican	0.1207	0.000472	255.56	0.0000	1.128	0.886
Asian	0.0659	0.000481	136.99	0.0000	1.068	0.936
Spanish	0.0998	0.002625	38.03	0.0000	1.105	0.905
OtherLanguage	-0.3198	0.000476	-672.13	0.0000	0.726	1.377
EnglishLearner	-0.0277	0.002707	-10.25	0.0000	0.973	1.028
DropoutRisk	1.2257	0.000947	1,294.43	0.0000	3.406	0.294
SpecialEducation	-0.2567	0.003557	-72.16	0.0000	0.774	1.293
Gifted	0.1847	0.000633	292.03	0.0000	1.203	0.831
LowIncome	0.1233	0.002374	51.93	0.0000	1.131	0.884
PreK	-0.0316	0.003364	-9.41	0.0000	0.969	1.032
PreKNonEligible	-0.0575	0.003551	-16.18	0.0000	0.944	1.059
PrimaryGradeEnrollment	0.3178	0.002557	124.28	0.0000	1.374	0.728
Mobility	0.1718	0.003669	46.82	0.0000	1.187	0.842
ReadingTestGrade3	-1.2153	0.000508	-2,390.21	0.0000	0.297	3.371
ReadingScoreGrade3	-0.0008	0.000007	-110.68	0.0000	0.999	1.001
MathTestGrade5	-1.7943	0.000480	-3,738.92	0.0000	0.166	6.015
MathScoreGrade5	-0.0010	0.000008	-123.54	0.0000	0.999	1.001
ReadingTestGrade6	-2.2864	0.000493	-4,637.43	0.0000	0.102	9.839
ReadingScoreGrade6	-0.0013	0.000008	-175.11	0.0000	0.999	1.001
MathTestGrade8	-2.4441	0.000480	-5,094.24	0.0000	0.087	11.520
MathScoreGrade8	-0.0029	0.000007	-420.47	0.0000	0.997	1.003

Large Odds Ratios (lower chance of graduating) include: *Male, Dropout Risk, Gifted, Primary Grade Enrollment, Mobility.*

Large Inverse Odds Ratios (higher chance of graduating) include: *Black, SpecialEducation, ReadingTestGrade3, MathTestGrade5, ReadingTestGrade6, MathTestGrade8.*

Figure 10: Bar graphs of coefficients, Z-Scores, odds ratios, and inverse odds ratios for Final Model, K12model6XNoUw, Still In School vs. Graduates

6. Results

6.1 High School Outcome Modeling Results for 1998 Kindergarten Cohort

The final model from the Cohort 2000 study, K12Model6NoUw, was also run on the 1998 Cohort to confirm transferability of the modeling approach and to compare results across different cohorts. Prediction results for Cohort 1998 including actual and predicted counts rates of correct classification overall and within categories are presented in Table 7. These results are similar to those obtained for the 2000 Cohort using the same model. The overall prediction rate for Cohort 1998 of .702 is not far from the .758 rate for Cohort 2000. For graduates, the Cohort 1998 rate is .797 for graduates, .369 for Dropouts/Other Leavers, and .689 for Still in School. This is comparable to the Cohort 2000 rates of .861, .321, and .765.

Table 7: Classification Performance is shown for Cohort 1998 Using Multinomial Logistic Model with Graduates as Reference Group. This model uses Weighted Estimation and Omits Observations with Unknown High School Outcomes.

K12Model6NoUw	Predicted Graduate	Predicted Dropout/Other Leaver	Predicted Still in School	Rate of Correct Classification
Actual Graduate	124,373	21,304	10,438	.797
Actual Dropout/OtherLeaver	11,841	15,911	15,405	.369
Actual Still In School	3,730	7,436	24,740	.689

Overall Correct Classification Rate = .702

Dropout/OtherLeaver

Large Odds Ratios (lower chance of graduating) include: *Male, Native American, Low Income, Mobility, MathTestGrade5.*

Large Inverse Odds Ratios (higher chance of graduating) include: *Black, Hispanic, Asian, OtherLanguage, SpecialEducation, PreK, ReadingTestGrade3, MathTestGrade5, ReadingTestGrade6, MathTestGrade8.*

Still In School

Large Odds Ratios (lower chance of graduating) include: *Male, Dropout Risk, Low Income, Mobility, MathTestGrade5, Primary Grade Enrollment, Mobility.*

Large Inverse Odds Ratios (higher chance of graduating) include: *Black, Asian, OtherLanguage, SpecialEducation, ReadingTestGrade3, MathTestGrade5, ReadingTestGrade6, MathTestGrade8.*

Table 8: Multinomial Logistic Model Results for Cohort 1998 using K12modelXnoUw for Dropouts/Leavers versus the On-Time Graduate Reference Group

DROPOUT/ OTHERLEAVER	Coef	StdError	Z	p	OR	1/OR
Male	0.1675	0.003416	49.04	0.0000	1.182	0.846
Black	-0.5361	0.002913	-184.01	0.0000	0.585	1.709
Hispanic	-0.2592	0.003417	-75.85	0.0000	0.772	1.295
NativeAmerican	0.2597	0.00052	499.32	0.0000	1.300	0.769
Asian	-0.3735	0.000519	-719.56	0.0000	0.688	1.453
Spanish	-0.0705	0.00287	-24.57	0.0000	0.932	1.073
OtherLanguage	-0.2601	0.000505	-514.62	0.0000	0.771	1.297
EnglishLearner	-0.0286	0.002981	-9.59	0.0000	0.972	1.029
DropoutRisk	0.0884	0.001427	61.92	0.0000	1.092	0.916
SpecialEducation	-0.4768	0.00408	-116.87	0.0000	0.621	1.610
Gifted	0.007	0.000872	8.07	0.0000	1.007	0.993
LowIncome	0.4676	0.002682	174.34	0.0000	1.596	0.627
PreK	-0.3763	0.003417	-110.11	0.0000	0.686	1.458
PreKNonEligible	-0.16	0.004047	-39.53	0.0000	0.852	1.174
PrimaryGradeEnroll	-0.0752	0.00241	-31.2	0.0000	0.928	1.078
Mobility	0.2836	0.00314	90.29	0.0000	1.330	0.752
ReadingTestGrade3	-0.635	0.000657	-966.28	0.0000	0.530	1.887
ReadingScoreGrade3	-0.007	0.000118	-59.44	0.0000	0.993	1.007
MathTestGrade5	0.6233	0.000554	1125.43	0.0000	1.865	0.536
MathScoreGrade5	0.0002	0.000007	25.07	0.0000	1.000	1.000
ReadingTestGrade6	-0.9512	0.000582	-1635.43	0.0000	0.386	2.591
ReadingScoreGrade6	-0.0004	0.000007	-55.46	0.0000	1.000	1.000
MathTestGrade8	-6.2063	0.00054	-11482.88	0.0000	0.002	495.880
MathScoreGrade8	-0.0039	0.000006	-666.39	0.0000	0.996	1.004

Large Odds Ratios (lower chance of graduating) include: *Male, Native American, Low Income, Mobility, MathTestGrade5.*

Large Inverse Odds Ratios (higher chance of graduating) include: *Black, Hispanic, Asian, OtherLanguage, SpecialEducation, PreK, ReadingTestGrade3, MathTestGrade5, ReadingTestGrade6, MathTestGrade8.*

Table 9: Multinomial Logistic Model Results for Cohort 1998 using K12modelXnoUw for Still In School versus the On-Time Graduate Reference Group

STILL IN SCHOOL	Coef	StdError	Z	p	OR	1/OR
Male	0.3796	0.002859	132.77	0.0000	1.462	0.684
Black	-0.1303	0.002553	-51.06	0.0000	0.878	1.139
Hispanic	0.0278	0.003394	8.18	0.0000	1.028	0.973
NativeAmerican	0.0723	0.000452	160.05	0.0000	1.075	0.930
Asian	-0.2672	0.000447	-597.51	0.0000	0.766	1.305
Spanish	-0.0237	0.002573	-9.20	0.0000	0.977	1.024
OtherLanguage	-0.1705	0.000445	-382.92	0.0000	0.843	1.186
EnglishLearner	0.1224	0.002664	45.94	0.0000	1.130	0.885
DropoutRisk	1.0242	0.000946	1,082.32	0.0000	2.785	0.359
SpecialEducation	-0.5563	0.003706	-150.10	0.0000	0.573	1.745
Gifted	0.0587	0.000614	95.56	0.0000	1.060	0.943
LowIncome	0.2750	0.002441	112.65	0.0000	1.317	0.759
PreK	-0.0237	0.003449	-6.87	0.0000	0.977	1.024
PreKNonEligible	-0.0274	0.003620	-7.56	0.0000	0.973	1.028
PrimaryGradeEnrollment	0.1680	0.002392	70.23	0.0000	1.183	0.845
Mobility	0.1957	0.003450	56.73	0.0000	1.216	0.822
ReadingTestGrade3	-0.2810	0.000561	-501.27	0.0000	0.755	1.325
ReadingScoreGrade3	-0.0007	0.000127	-5.75	0.0000	0.999	1.001
MathTestGrade5	-0.4892	0.000454	-1,077.48	0.0000	0.613	1.631
MathScoreGrade5	-0.0007	0.000008	-85.97	0.0000	0.999	1.001
ReadingTestGrade6	-2.8018	0.000470	-5,956.41	0.0000	0.061	16.393
ReadingScoreGrade6	-0.0016	0.000008	-204.43	0.0000	0.998	1.002
MathTestGrade8	-7.8628	0.000451	-17,438.17	0.0000	0.00038	2598.8
MathScoreGrade8	-0.0049	0.000006	-763.44	0.0000	0.995	1.005

Large Odds Ratios (lower chance of graduating) include: *Male, Dropout Risk, Low Income, Mobility, Primary Grade Enrollment, Mobility.*

Large Inverse Odds Ratios (higher chance of graduating) include: *Black, Asian, OtherLanguage, SpecialEducation, ReadingTestGrade3, MathTestGrade5, ReadingTestGrade6, MathTestGrade8.*

6.2 High School Outcome Modeling Results for 1995 Kindergarten Cohort

As was done previously for Cohort 1998, the final model from the Cohort 2000 study, K12Model6NoUw, was also run on the 1995 Cohort to confirm transferability of the modeling approach and to compare results across different cohorts. Prediction results for Cohort 1995 including actual and predicted counts rates of correct classification overall and within categories are presented in Table 10. These results are similar to, but a little worse than, those obtained for the 1998 and 2000 Cohorts using the same model, but are certainly within the same ballpark. The overall prediction rate for Cohort 1995 of .649 is a little lower than the value of .702 for Cohort 1998 and even further away from the .758 rate for Cohort 2000. For graduates, the Cohort 1995 rate is .759 for graduates, .370 for Dropouts/Other Leavers, and .609 for Still in School. This is at least comparable to the Cohort 1998 rates of .797, .369, and .689 and the Cohort 2000 rates of .861, .321, and .765.

Table 10: Classification Performance is shown for Cohort 1995 Using Multinomial Logistic Model with Graduates as Reference Group. This model uses Weighted Estimation and Omits Observations with Unknown High School Outcomes.

K12Model6NoUw	Predicted Graduate	Predicted Dropout/Other Leaver	Predicted Still in School	Rate of Correct Classification
Actual Graduate	98,820	19,748	11,598	.759
Actual Dropout/OtherLeaver	11,725	17,275	17,646	.370
Actual Still In School	4,222	8,249	19,404	.609

Overall Correct Classification Rate = .649

Table 11: Multinomial Logistic Model Results for Cohort 1995 using K12modelXnoUw for Dropouts/Other Leavers versus the On-Time Graduate Reference Group

DROPOUT/						
OTHERLEAVER	Coef	StdError	Z	p	LOR	inv LOR
Male	0.164282	0.0073	22.60	0.0000	1.179	0.849
Black	-0.437566	0.0074	-58.87	0.0000	0.646	1.549
Hispanic	-0.124650	0.0068	-18.29	0.0000	0.883	1.133
NativeAmerican	0.078835	0.0014	56.93	0.0000	1.082	0.924
Asian	-0.360083	0.0033	-110.35	0.0000	0.698	1.433
Spanish	-0.015527	0.0074	-2.10	0.0353	0.985	1.016
OtherLanguage	-0.231414	0.0042	-55.17	0.0000	0.793	1.260
EnglishLearner	-0.061801	0.0071	-8.72	0.0000	0.940	1.064
DropoutRisk	0.036086	0.0086	4.20	0.0000	1.037	0.965
SpecialEducation	-0.357820	0.0079	-45.44	0.0000	0.699	1.430
Gifted	-0.088841	0.0081	-10.92	0.0000	0.915	1.093
LowIncome	0.569652	0.0081	69.90	0.0000	1.768	0.566
PreK	-0.311676	0.0063	-49.57	0.0000	0.732	1.366
PreKNonEligible	-0.086109	0.0081	-10.65	0.0000	0.917	1.090
PrimaryGradeEnrollment	-0.108955	0.0044	-24.65	0.0000	0.897	1.115
Mobility	0.279496	0.0036	77.54	0.0000	1.322	0.756
ReadingTestGrade3	-0.043840	0.0051	-8.57	0.0000	0.957	1.045
ReadingScoreGrade3	-0.001198	0.0001	-8.30	0.0000	0.999	1.001
MathTestGrade5	-2.350541	0.0031	-767.83	0.0000	0.095	10.491
MathScoreGrade5	-0.026571	0.0002	-163.07	0.0000	0.974	1.027
ReadingTestGrade6	-2.253994	0.0046	-494.48	0.0000	0.105	9.526
ReadingScoreGrade6	-0.024366	0.0002	-148.35	0.0000	0.976	1.025
MathTestGrade8	-6.110440	0.0016	-3854.60	0.0000	0.002	450.537
MathScoreGrade8	-0.003899	0.0000	-784.43	0.0000	0.996	1.004

Large Odds Ratios (lower chance of graduating) include: *Male, LowIncome, Mobility.*

Large Inverse Odds Ratios (higher chance of graduating) include: *Black, Asian, OtherLanguage, SpecialEducation, PreK, Mobility, MathTestGrade5, ReadingTestGrade6, MathTestGrade8.*

Table 12: Multinomial Logistic Model Results for Cohort 1998 using K12modelXnoUw for Still In School versus the On-Time Graduate Reference Group

STILL IN SCHOOL	Coef	StdError	Z	p	LOR	Inv OR
Male	0.408552	0.0078	52.59	0.0000	1.505	0.665
Black	0.029208	0.0072	4.06	0.0000	1.030	0.971
Hispanic	0.157500	0.0068	23.31	0.0000	1.171	0.854
NativeAmerican	-0.028521	0.0013	-21.90	0.0000	0.972	1.029
Asian	-0.192015	0.0029	-66.72	0.0000	0.825	1.212
Spanish	-0.007282	0.0070	-1.05	0.2954	0.993	1.007
OtherLanguage	-0.144960	0.0038	-38.08	0.0000	0.865	1.156
EnglishLearner	0.024122	0.0072	3.36	0.0008	1.024	0.976
DropoutRisk	1.119566	0.0053	212.23	0.0000	3.064	0.326
SpecialEducation	-0.091481	0.0080	-11.44	0.0000	0.913	1.096
Gifted	-0.252696	0.0059	-42.57	0.0000	0.777	1.287
LowIncome	0.332721	0.0079	41.96	0.0000	1.395	0.717
PreK	-0.065857	0.0065	-10.11	0.0000	0.936	1.068
PreKNonEligible	0.030497	0.0085	3.59	0.0003	1.031	0.970
PrimaryGradeEnrollment	0.019001	0.0048	3.96	0.0001	1.019	0.981
Mobility	0.226724	0.0038	59.27	0.0000	1.254	0.797
ReadingTestGrade3	0.091985	0.0049	18.95	0.0000	1.096	0.912
ReadingScoreGrade3	-0.002078	0.0001	-13.87	0.0000	0.998	1.002
MathTestGrade5	-1.891132	0.0028	-673.21	0.0000	0.151	6.627
MathScoreGrade5	-0.019710	0.0002	-116.46	0.0000	0.980	1.020
ReadingTestGrade6	-1.818658	0.0042	-429.13	0.0000	0.162	6.164
ReadingScoreGrade6	-0.015033	0.0002	-87.77	0.0000	0.985	1.015
MathTestGrade8	-8.526776	0.0014	-6135.18	0.0000	0.000	5048.144
MathScoreGrade8	-0.005532	0.0000	-1079.00	0.0000	0.994	1.006

Large Odds Ratios (lower chance of graduating) include: *Male, Hispanic, DropoutRisk, LowIncome, Mobility.*

Large Inverse Odds Ratios (higher chance of graduating) include: *Asian, OtherLanguage, Gifted, MathTestGrade5, ReadingTestGrade6, MathTestGrade8.*

6.3 Results for Higher Education Modeling

For the 2000 cohort, some demonstration models for Higher Education were run to address the modeling needs of the later portion of the educational path, as shown in the diagrams provided earlier for the graphical model. As noted above, separate models are needed for the separate stages of the STEM pathway. The goal was to apply the modeling approach that was developed for the K12 outcomes to selected Higher Education Outcomes. The sets of predictors included some of the same variables used to model High School Outcomes. In addition, some variables associated with high school coursework were added that appeared relevant to successful Higher Education Completion and STEM Degree outcomes.

Three different Outcome Variables were considered:

HighestCompletion

HighestCompletionEnroll (restricted to those who enrolled in Year 1 following High School)

HighestCompletionGENroll (restricted to those who graduated on time and enrolled in Year 1 following High School)

Model fitting was implemented with three different sets of education factors included in the input variable set.

Input Set 1: Male, Black, Hispanic, NativeAmerican, Asian, Spanish, OtherLanguage, EnglishLearner, DropoutRisk, SpecialEducation, Gifted, Low Income

Input Set 2: Male, Black, Hispanic, NativeAmerican, Asian, Spanish, Other Language, EnglishLearner, DropoutRisk, Special Education, Gifted, Low Income, PreK, PreKNonEligible, Retention, Enrollment, Primary Enrollment, Mobility, ReadingTestGrade3, ReadingScoreGrade3, MathTestGrade5, MathScoreGrade5, ReadingTestGrade6, ReadingScoreGrade6, MathTestGrade8, MathScoreGrade8, NumMathCourses, NumScienceCourses, APCompSci, MetCCRStdG11RTest, MetCCRStdG11RScore, MetComStdG11MTest, MetComStdG11MScore

Input Set 3: Male, Black, Hispanic, NativeAmerican, Asian, Spanish, Other Language, EnglishLearner, DropoutRisk, Special Education, Gifted, Low Income, PreK, PreKNonEligible, Retention, Enrollment, Primary Enrollment, Mobility, ReadingTestGrade3, ReadingScoreGrade3, MathTestGrade5, MathScoreGrade5, ReadingTestGrade6, ReadingScoreGrade6, MathTestGrade8, MathScoreGrade8, NumMathCourses, NumScienceCourses, APCompSci, MetCCRStdG11RTest, MetCCRStdG11RScore, MetComStdG11MTest, MetComStdG11MScore, Algebra1inMS, CollegeLevelMathHighest, PreCalcHighest, Algebra2Highest, LessThanAlg2Highest, APCalculus, NumCollegeLevelScience, APPHysics, STEMCTESemesters

As with the K12 STEM pathway from Kindergarten to High School Graduation, a Multinomial Model can be used to model the path from High School Graduation to Higher Education Completion to see which variables are relevant and to see how well the outcomes could be predicted. One of the Higher Education models that has been implemented is HEmodel3GENrollw, a model of Highest Completion restricted to On-time High School Graduates who enrolled in Higher Education within 1 year, as a

function of the predictors in Input Set 3 using weighted estimation. Sample size is 112,229. Prediction Performance Results are presented in Table 13a. As a comparison, HEModel3w was fit using the same predictors in Input Set 3 to the outcome HighestCompletion which includes all 265,368 students in the cohort. Results are presented in Table 13b.

Table 13a: Classification Performance is shown for Higher Education Model for HighestCompletionGENroll using Multinomial Logistic Model with No Completion as Reference Group. This model uses Weighted Estimation.

HEModel3GENrollw	Predicted No Degree	Predicted Certificate	Predicted Associate's Degree	Predicted Bachelor's Degree	Rate of Correct Classification
Actual No Degree	18,273	15,610	8,396	10,949	.343
Actual Certificate	1,412	2,690	1,053	802	.452
Actual Associate's Degree	2,462	3,307	2,891	2,926	.250
Actual Bachelor's Degree	4,930	2,901	6,091	27,536	.664

Overall Correct Classification Rate = .458

Table 13b: Classification Performance is shown for Higher Education Model for HighestCompletion using Multinomial Logistic Model with No Completion as Reference Group. This model uses Weighted Estimation

HEModel3w	Predicted No Degree	Predicted Certificate	Predicted Associate's Degree	Predicted Bachelor's Degree	Rate of Correct Classification
Actual No Degree	103,271	43,905	27,282	20,705	.529
Actual Certificate	2,253	4,105	2,243	1,300	.533
Actual Associate's Degree	2,025	3,978	4,812	3,944	.326
Actual Bachelor's Degree	3,242	3,406	8,757	30,140	.662

Overall Correct Classification Rate = .542

Table 14: Higher Education Model HEmodel3GEnrollw - HighestCompletion
 By On-Time High School Graduates Enrolled in Year 1 following High School:
 Large Odds Ratios are in Green, Large Inverse Odds Ratios are in Yellow for
 Certificate, Associate's Degree, and Bachelor's Degree VS No Degree.

HEmodel3GEnrollw	CERT OR	CERT 1/OR	ASSOC OR	ASSOC 1/OR	BACH OR	BACH 1/OR
Male	0.623	1.606	0.641	1.560	0.498	2.008
Black	0.611	1.637	0.588	1.702	1.056	0.947
Hispanic	1.111	0.900	1.100	0.909	0.919	1.088
NativeAmerican	0.806	1.241	1.243	0.805	0.940	1.064
Asian	0.937	1.067	0.889	1.125	1.129	0.886
Spanish	1.136	0.880	1.125	0.889	1.118	0.895
OtherLanguage	0.825	1.212	1.444	0.692	1.846	0.542
EnglishLearner	1.266	0.790	1.282	0.780	1.491	0.671
DropoutRisk	1.054	0.948	0.935	1.070	0.708	1.412
SpecialEducation	1.038	0.963	1.110	0.901	1.131	0.884
Gifted	0.853	1.172	0.821	1.217	0.901	1.109
LowIncome	1.013	0.987	0.938	1.066	0.473	2.116
PreK	0.972	1.028	1.086	0.921	1.264	0.791
PreKNonEligible	1.011	0.989	0.996	1.004	1.014	0.986
Retention	0.979	1.022	0.563	1.777	0.363	2.754
Enrollment	1.017	0.984	0.986	1.014	0.974	1.026
PrimaryGradeEnrollment	1.064	0.940	1.061	0.942	1.023	0.978
Mobility	0.924	1.082	0.900	1.111	0.823	1.216
ReadingTestGrade3	0.650	1.538	0.693	1.442	1.786	0.560
ReadingScoreGrade3	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
MathTestGrade5	0.649	1.540	1.269	0.788	1.132	0.883
MathScoreGrade5	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
ReadingTestGrade6	0.417	2.401	1.237	0.808	12.785	0.078
ReadingScoreGrade6	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.001	0.999
MathTestGrade8	0.919	1.088	3.303	0.303	18.641	0.054
MathScoreGrade8	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.001	0.999
NumMathCourses	1.049	0.954	1.101	0.908	1.196	0.836
NumScienceCourses	1.002	0.998	1.052	0.951	1.059	0.944
APCompSci	0.923	1.084	0.659	1.519	0.852	1.173
MetCCRStdG11RDummy	1.257	0.795	0.826	1.211	0.749	1.335
MetCCRStdG11RImpute	0.851	1.175	1.063	0.941	1.548	0.646
MetComStdG11MDummy	0.749	1.335	1.321	0.757	1.762	0.567
MetComStdG11MImpute	0.972	1.029	1.033	0.968	1.386	0.722
Algebra1inMS	0.981	1.020	1.118	0.895	1.254	0.798
CollegeLevelMathHighest	1.626	0.615	1.230	0.813	0.802	1.248
PreCalcHighest	1.757	0.569	1.001	0.999	0.505	1.981
Algebra2Highest	1.784	0.561	0.830	1.205	0.292	3.428
LessThanAlg2Highest	1.664	0.601	0.570	1.754	0.170	5.877
APCalculus	0.681	1.468	0.632	1.582	0.929	1.076

NumCollegeLevelScience	0.777	1.287	0.832	1.202	1.328	0.753
APPPhysics	0.873	1.146	1.002	0.998	0.757	1.321
STEMCTESemesters	0.998	1.002	1.007	0.993	0.970	1.031

Table 14 provides a list of variables with large Odds Ratios highlighted in green and large Inverse Odds Ratios highlighted in yellow for the following three comparisons: 1) Certificate relative to No Completion, 2) Associate’s Degree relative to No Completion, and 3) Bachelor’s Degree Relative to No Completion. There does not seem to be an obvious pattern to these larger values, and it is unclear how to characterize these results. There do seem to be a number of large ratios associated with demographic variables and high school courses and test scores.

In general, the Higher Ed models are less developed than the other models that were studied. This may be why the predictive power was somewhat lower than for the other models, and the results from examining the odds ratios seemed less clear. There may also be more variability present at the higher education level than the K12 level. This model compares different degree completion levels to no degree. An alternative analysis using Bachelor’s Completion might prove to be more informative.

7. Discussion of Results and Implications

The results obtained from the multinomial logistic modeling demonstrate the feasibility of this approach for modeling the probabilities of different high school and higher education outcomes. The results include information about factors which impact the likelihood of different student outcomes that can be considered for follow-up in future modeling studies and potentially used as input to educational decision-making. While additional study and verification of the factors identified by the models is recommended, knowledge of which factors affect students with different attributes could be a powerful source of information for addressing the needs of students and helping them to achieve successful outcomes such as on-time high school graduation, higher education degree completion, and STEM degree completion in particular. Putting knowledge about different effects into action can pave the way for increasing the number of individuals who complete high school, college, and STEM degrees.

8. Potential Future Research

Perspectives gained from executing this study can be used to suggest potential areas for further exploration and refinement of the K12 and Higher Education models. As experience in modeling this type of data expands, additional variables, data sets, and new sources of information could be incorporated.

The Lasso modeling approach and other variable selection methods would allow more rapid examination of models containing different subsets from the available set of variables. Applying these methods might lead to new insights about variables that impact high school outcomes, higher education degree completion, and STEM degree

completion. Another benefit would be the ability to examine large numbers of potential interactions.

Development of a more sophisticated framework to simultaneously model the path probabilities and the parameters for the outcome models might capture dependencies in the overall STEM production system that have not yet been addressed.

Prediction rates could potentially be improved through development of strategies for selecting different weights or tuning the category splitting in the multinomial logistic regression. In addition, verification of the modeling and prediction results should include model fitting to different data from that used in training the model, either by obtaining new data or by splitting available data into training samples and samples for testing out-of-sample prediction performance.

To make results more useful and relevant, the variable selection process could be altered to incorporate higher weighting of variables that are either thought to be important or appropriate for adjustment and control in the actual educational setting.

9. Summary

This investigation was a feasibility study to explore the use of analytics approaches to examine the outcomes from the education and learning process with the goal of developing a better understanding of the process for improving student outcomes and increasing the production of trained individuals with STEM degrees. The pipeline for STEM degrees was represented by a multi-stage graphical model that allowed the process to be broken into a series of components whose outcomes could each be modeled as a function of available predictors. Data was examined for three different cohorts of students from the Texas public school system that started kindergarten in 1995, 1998, and 2000. A modeling study was conducted using multinomial logistic regression for the 2000 cohort data, and the selected model was also applied to the 1995 and 1998 cohorts. This approach can be used to provide information for identifying factors that impact the successful pursuit of on-time high school graduation, higher education degree completion, STEM degree completion, and other learning outcomes. This feasibility study has successfully demonstrated the use of multinomial logistic regression for investigating educational outcomes at the high school and higher education levels.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by funding provided by the University of Texas System. Data provided by the Texas Education Research Center was critical to the analysis performed in this investigation.

The research team wishes to acknowledge the insights and comments provided by Jon Fleming and Steven Stringer throughout the development and execution of this project.

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Appendix – Variables Available for K12 Modeling

Variable	Name in Analysis/ Models	Purpose in Model	Variable Description Including Modeling Comparison Group
High School Outcome	HSOutcome	Outcome	For TX public school students in a kindergarten cohort, which of the 5 outcomes they had
Graduate	HSOutcome:Graduate (1)	Outcome	Graduated high school on time or early
Dropout	HSOutcome:Dropout (2)	Outcome	Dropped out of school in 7th grade or later, nearly all occurred in high school
Other Leaver	HSOutcome:OtherLeaver (3)	Outcome	Left school in Grade 7 or later for reason other than dropping out (e.g., moving out of TX or homeschooling)
Still in School	HSOutcome:StillinSchool (4)	Outcome	Still enrolled in school in on-time HS graduation year but did not graduate
Unknown	HSOutcome:Unknown (5)	Outcome	None of the above outcomes, usually because left school prior to 7th grade, years in which TX does not track reason for leaving
Male	Male	Input	Result for male students, as compared to females
Asian	Asian	Input	Result for Asian students, as compared to White, non-Hispanic students
Black	Black	Input	Result for Black students, as compared to White, non-Hispanic students
Hispanic	Hispanic	Input	Results for Hispanic students, as compared to White, non-Hispanic students
Native American	NativeAmerican	Input	Results for Native American students, as compared to White, non-Hispanic students
Spanish	SpanishAtHome	Input	Results for students who spoke Spanish at home in kindergarten, as compared to those who spoke English at home
Other language	OtherLangAtHome	Input	Results for students who spoke a language other than Spanish or English at home in kindergarten, as compared to those who spoke English at home
English Learner	ELLEver	Input	Results for students designated as an English Language Learner in any year enrolled, as compared to English speakers
Dropout Risk	AT RISKEver	Input	Results for students designated at risk of dropping out in any year enrolled, as compared to not at risk
Special Education	SPECEDEver	Input	Results for students with a special education designation in any year enrolled, as compared to students not in special education
Gifted	GIFTEDEver	Input	Results for students in the Gifted and Talented program in any year enrolled, as compared to students not in program
Low Income	LowIncomeEver	Input	Results for students from a family designated as low income based on income < 185% of the poverty line in any year in any year enrolled, as compared to students from non-low-income families

Pre-K	PreKENrollY	Input	Pre-K is an optional grade. Children who are low income and/or English learners are eligible to attend Pre-K at no cost to the family. Results are for students who were eligible for Pre-K and enrolled in Pre-K, as compared to those who were eligible but didn't enroll
Pre-K Non-eligible	PreKNotElig	Input	Results for students who were ineligible for 'free' Pre-K because they were non-low-income English speakers (whether or not they paid and enrolled in Pre-K), as compared to those who were eligible but didn't enroll
Grade Retention	RetainedEVER	Input	Results of students who were retained in the same grade at least once from kindergarten through the next 12 years, compared to students on the normal grade progression (who are in 12th grade 12 years after kindergarten)
Enrollment	NumYearsEnrolledK12	Input	Results based on the number of years a student was enrolled in public school in TX from K to 12th grade
Primary Grade Enrollment	NumYearsEnrolledG1to6	Input	Results are based on the number of years a student was enrolled in Texas public schools in Grades 1 to 6
Mobility	NumSchoolDistrictsEver	Input	Results based on the number of school districts (ISD or Charter) students were enrolled in; the more school districts, the more mobile the student
Reading Test Grade 3	ScaledScoreG3RDummy	Input	Results based on students who had a score for the 3rd grade reading state standardized test (TAAS for 1995, 1998; TAKS for 2000 cohorts), compared to students without a valid score
Reading Score Grade 3	ScaledScoreG3RImpute	Input	Results based on students' 3rd grade reading standardized test scores, for students who had a valid score
Math Test Grade 5	ScaledScoreG5MDummy	Input	Results based on students who had a score for the 5th grade math state standardized test (TAAS for 1995; TAKS for 1998, 2000 cohorts), compared to students without a valid score
Math Score Grade 5	ScaledScoreG5MImpute	Input	Results based on students' 5th grade math standardized test scores, for students who had a valid score
Reading Test Grade 6	ScaledScoreG6RDummy	Input	Results based on students who had a score for the 6th grade reading state standardized test (TAAS for 1995; TAKS for 1998, 2000 cohorts), compared to students without a valid score
Reading Score Grade 6	ScaledScoreG36RImpute	Input	Results based on students' 6th grade reading standardized test scores, for students who had a valid score
Math Test Grade 8	ScaledScoreG8MDummy	Input	Results based on students who had a score for the 8th grade math state standardized test (TAKS), compared to students without a valid score
Math Score Grade 8	ScaledScoreG8MImpute	Input	Results based on students' 8th grade math standardized test scores, for students who had a valid score